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WP3: Consultancy & User Groups

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Executive Summary

BioExcel targets a broad and heterogeneous group of users from the biomolecular research community. Different kinds of consultancy and support will work best with different communities. In this project we have explored potential consultancy models through pilot use cases, contributed to a number of proposals for further related activities, and built solid foundations for future professional consultancy by building trust with potential customers.

The project ran five Pilot Use Cases (UCs) which had an important role in bringing together work from across the project. The UC *Alchemical Free Energy Calculations in Biomolecules* covered the field of Free Energy Calculations, in which there is currently strong interest in the wider community, including drug discovery by pharmaceutical companies. It linked GROMACS with pmx, both codes being supported by BioExcel. *Molecular Recognition*, introduced a test bed where two BioExcel codes (HADDOCK and GROMACS) were used within the same automated workflow using the platform MDstudio, which will help to scale up and harvest of HPC/HTC resources in a simplified way. *Virtual Screening* was a collaboration with Nostrum Biodiscovery to study an important drug discovery process. *Multi-scale modeling* focused on validating a new highly parallel QM/MM interface of CPMD by applying the code to a state-of-the-art problem and comparing main results with the simulations performed with the original CPMD QM/MM interface. *Rapid turnaround cancer analysis pipeline for high throughput sequencing data* brought together existing processes into a new automated workflow and evaluated its suitability for an HPC implementation.

The process of engaging with communities (and potential future customers) has been a gradual one. After an initial community landscaping exercise, several activities were begun to engage with communities of interest. Webinars proved a successful mechanism to begin engagement from the outset of the project; support forums provided a way for us to support existing users of the project's codes from the start. As the project developed, there were opportunities to engage with communities face-to-face in smaller workshop meetings and the Community Forum, which was designed to bring members of different interest groups together.

As well as supporting the wider community, considerable groundwork has been put in place to build a capability to offer professional consultancy, building trust with potential future customers. This groundwork included site visits and customised training for pharmaceutical companies such as Janssen and UCB. In addition, the project's pilot use cases have provided insight into possible consultancy models and services such as webinars, forums and events which simultaneously allowed us to support best practice, share information about the centre, and learn more about the needs of the communities.

The project has also provided opportunities for partners to engage in a number of new proposals, such as the consortium for Integrative Modelling of Antibodies (IMAbs) which includes UCB, AstraZeneca and MedImmune, some of which have led into further use-case work in BioExcel-2 which includes topics of specific interest to potential future industry clients.

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1 Introduction

The BioExcel CoE aims to support excellence in computational biomolecular research. There are many different ways in which a centre such as BioExcel can interact with the communities that it supports, and these are discussed in more detail in D3.5¹. We have previously surveyed the landscape of relevant user communities which spans maturity of user from entry-level users to advanced, location of users in universities, national and international institutions, not for profit organisations and private industry such as biopharmaceutical and agri-food companies (see D3.1²).

Consultancy is one important way that BioExcel can work with these communities. The term “consultancy” can be understood in different ways: In its narrowest sense, it is understood to be contracted, (usually) short-term work for a paying client to offer advice or a solution to a specific problem. Here the user is likely to be located in private industry. Beyond this narrow group of users, consultancy encompasses a variety of different means to support the wider user communities to understand their needs, to provide relevant expertise, guidance and sharing of best practice.

BioExcel aims to address this broad, heterogeneous group of users from academia and industry, and from early-career researchers to experts. This makes it necessary to explore different ways of supporting and working with a network of partners and collaborators. Our belief is that by fostering such support and collaboration with users in industry this will open up opportunities for providing such services for a fee. Initially this will cover costs and later, have the potential to generate positive revenue which can be reinvested to sustain the centre as described in the sustainability plan in D5.4³.

So, it is in this context that we describe the consultancy support work undertaken by the centre which can be split broadly into two related areas. On the one hand, the partners in BioExcel have engaged in numerous projects and proposals with strong connections to the centre’s activities. Many of these have been discussed already in the precursor to this document, *D3.2: Consultancy Proposals*⁴. The other area is the pilot use cases that have been explored during this project. The pilot use cases have had a dual purpose: they have undertaken valuable work in their own right, and they have also allowed us to explore ways in which the Centre could collaborate with, or offer consultancy to, external parties in the future.

This project has successfully established the BioExcel Centre of Excellence, but there is much work still to do. The initial project to establish the Centre (which we

¹ Consultancy Modalities and Funding Options, Final Update, BioExcel Deliverable 3.5. In preparation. Available from www.bioexcel.eu from January 2019.

² Selection and Establishment of User Groups, BioExcel Deliverable 3.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.264011>

³ Governance and Business Plan, BioExcel Deliverable D5.4. In preparation, due Dec. 31 2018.

⁴ Consultancy Proposals, BioExcel Deliverable D3.2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.574607>

refer to in this document as *BioExcel-1*) is now coming to a close after three years, but the Centre (*BioExcel*) will continue, supported by a follow-on project (herein referred to as *BioExcel-2*) funded by the European Commission. In the longer term, it is expected that the Centre will be supported by a combination of public funding and funding from other sources. Details of the sustainability and business planning are covered in D5.4.

In this document, we describe the work undertaken in the BioExcel project which has been undertaken with collaborators and the wider community to explore future consultancy models and lay the groundwork for future collaboration. We first describe some specific activities that have been worked in WP3. We start with the pilot use cases from the project, and then describe a number of mini projects that were started later in the project to respond to various opportunities, with emphasis on support for user needs. We then step back and consider the progress that we have made in terms of positioning ourselves to offer services, including consultancy, to BioExcel's target communities.

2 Pilot Use Cases

BioExcel-1 started with seven pilot use cases. In response to the first project review, a decision was made to focus on a smaller number of use cases. We sought to maintain a balance between *focus* (ensuring that we had sufficient resources to undertake quality work in the use cases we were exploring) and *breadth* (to try to ensure that BioExcel establishes itself as Centre for *all* of Computational Biomolecular Research). Some of these pilot use cases are therefore more stand-alone, in that they explore areas beyond the core focus of the Centre's current work, and some of them serve to bring together activities from other parts of the project, to apply code development from WP1 and to provide example workflows developed in WP2.

The Pilot Use Cases are listed in Table 1. The work undertaken in the use cases was selected because it was scientifically interesting, but also to explore different types of work that could be undertaken in future collaborations. This table highlights why the work is of interest as a pilot. (The UC numbering in brackets links to numbering of these use cases in previous deliverables).

Table 1: Summary of Pilot Use Cases

Use Case	Summary
Free Energy Simulations of Biomolecular Complexes (UC2)	Interesting as this UC covers the field of Free Energy Calculations, in which there is currently strong interest in the wider community, including drug discovery by pharmaceutical companies. This links GROMACS with <i>pmx</i> , both codes being supported by BioExcel.
Biomolecular Recognition (UC4)	Introduces a test bed where two BioExcel flagship software (HADDOCK and GROMACS) are used within the same automated workflow. This workflow platform,

	MDstudio, will allow scale up and harvest of HPC/HTC resources in a transparent and simplified way for the users.
Virtual Screening (UC5)	Virtual screening is a computational technique used in the early phases of a drug discovery in almost every pharmaceutical company nowadays. The collaboration with Nostrum Biodiscovery in the development process of this pilot use case can help BioExcel in approaching these companies.
Multi-scale modeling of molecular basis for odor and taste (UC3)	Allows to validate the new and highly parallel QM/MM interface of CPMD developed during the BioExcel-1 project by applying the code to a state-of-the-art problem and comparing main results with the simulations performed with the original QM/MM interface of CPMD.
High Throughput Workflow for Cancer Genome Sequencing Data (UC1)	Brings together existing processes and techniques used in genomics into a sequencing workflow which, if executed quickly at scale, could support novel research and, potentially, clinical applications. Interesting in that it covers genomics, and that it covers a workflow and tools that have not traditionally used large-scale HPC, but which have the potential to scale up.

We now look at each use case in turn, summarising the work that has been done, highlighting how this supports the user needs and what has been learned from the use case in their role as pilots.

2.1 Free Energy Simulations of Biomolecular Complexes (UC2)

The alchemical free energy calculation framework, termed pmx⁵, allowing for amino acid and nucleic acid mutations as well as ligand modifications was being developed over the course of the BioExcel-1 project in the scope of WP1. The automated setup of the otherwise technically challenging free energy simulations enables performing large scale mutation scans in assessing protein stability, protein-protein or protein-DNA binding affinities and relative ligand binding free energies. Accurate estimation of biomolecular stabilities and binding affinities is of particular need in the areas of protein engineering, antibody design, ligand optimization or potential drug candidate identification. Development of the pmx software package in the WP1 yielded a framework which can be used to perform large scale amino acid, nucleic acid and ligand modification scans. Having this powerful machinery in place, in WP3 we concentrated on two activities: firstly, an online web-server was developed to facilitate the usage of pmx framework and, secondly, an extensive study into protein-DNA binding affinity changes was carried out. Later in the project, a collaboration with Janssen Pharmaceutica was established, and additional work was undertaken. Together, these activities make up the use case.

⁵ <http://pmx.mpibpc.mpg.de>

While the *pmx* tools can be executed from the command line, the barrier to use the software may be lowered by providing a user-friendly web interface. The *pmx* webserver⁵ was developed to allow for an easy to use hybrid structure/topology generation for amino acid and nucleotide mutations. The web-server allows choosing any mutation in the *pmx* supported force fields. In addition, inputs for the whole protein/DNA mutation scans can be generated. Furthermore, we provide online access to the pre-calculated database of the amino acid mutation free energies in tripeptides, which serve as a good approximation for an unfolded protein state and can be used in protein stability assessment. Documentation is available on the web-server itself, and details are available in Gapsys & de Groot (2017a)⁶.

Providing *pmx* software as a web-service has an additional value to the CoE, as it gives a possibility for more users to run free energy calculations. Having a technically demanding setup may discourage users from using the software. The webserver reduces the complexity of free energy calculation setup by performing many complex tasks under the hood, i.e. hidden from the user. Furthermore, as the webserver usage grows, there will be more feedback from the community of users. This way the developers learn more about the needs and issues that the users experience when dealing with the alchemical free energy calculations. While currently the *pmx* web-server supports amino acid and nucleic acid mutations, the inclusion of ligand modification is of high interest for the scientific community, especially pharmaceutical companies engaged in drug discovery. Further developments in this direction ought to be pursued within the scope of BioExcel-2 CoE. Although the development and maintenance of the web-based services are more demanding than that of a command line tool, the online services expand the software user base as well as increase visibility of the CoE.

The second part of this use case involved applying the software to a simulation which benefits from automation with *pmx*. The simulation was performed to learn what level of accuracy could be achieved in predicting protein-DNA binding affinity changes upon nucleotide mutation. For the simulation setup, we employed an automated *pmx* based hybrid DNA nucleotide structure/topology generation functionality. This automation of the procedure allowed performing a large-scale scan in 16 protein-DNA complexes comprising 397 mutations in total. The overall results reveal that with current-generation force fields we are able to reach accuracy of 5.6 kJ/mol in average unsigned error between calculation and experimental measurement. This accuracy is comparable to the quality of predictions that is achievable for protein stability changes upon amino acid mutation. Furthermore, we demonstrate that the free energy calculations are capable of providing reliable protein-DNA binding profiles. The methodology and results of this use case are described in Gapsys & de Groot (2017b)⁷.

⁶ V. Gapsys & B. de Groot, *pmx Webserver: A User Friendly Interface for Alchemy*, J. Chem. Inf. Model. **57** (2017); <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.6b00498>

⁷ V. Gapsys & B. de Groot, *Alchemical Free Energy Calculations for Nucleotide Mutations in Protein-DNA Complexes*, J. Chem. Theory Comput., **13** (2017); <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.7b00849>

The third part of this use case involves alchemical free energy calculations which was launched in collaboration with Janssen Pharmaceutica. This work started during the BioExcel-1 period (in March, 2018) and will be continued during the BioExcel-2 project.

The aim of this collaboration is an in-depth investigation into the application of GROMACS and pmx, for the automated assessment of free energy of ligand binding to target proteins. In the first step of the study we examined a number of ligand parameterization protocols identifying the optimal procedure for the subsequent large scale analysis. The most promising results were obtained by combining estimates from several force fields: the same effect has been previously observed for the amino acid and nucleotide mutations. The pmx and GROMACS based free energy calculations utilizing the non-equilibrium simulation protocol performed on par with the state-of-art commercial software. This is illustrated in Fig 1, where average unsigned errors (AUE) between the calculated and experimentally measured free energy differences are shown for a set of PDE2 inhibitors⁸. The pmx based calculations yield lower difference to the experimental measurements than the values obtained using Schrödinger's Maestro FEP+ package. These first insights into the ligand-protein binding free energy calculations provide a solid basis for the further large scale investigation within the framework of BioExcel-2.

Fig 1. Average unsigned error (AUE) between the calculated and experimentally measured free energy differences for a set of PDE2 inhibitors.

This use case allowed us to establish a close collaboration with Janssen Pharmaceutica working on inhibitors of phosphodiesterase 2 (PDE2). Throughout the course of the investigation we had frequent (weekly or bi-weekly exchanges). The data, results, as well as developed protocols and software were exchanged by both sides. The progress was discussed by email communication and via monthly calls. The collaboration is particularly fruitful in terms of the novel ideas and research opportunities. Several new directions for applying alchemical free

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-23039-5>

energy calculations are being discussed with Janssen Pharmaceutica. We are open to new collaborations of similar format, e.g. UCB has expressed an interest in the free energy calculations and we are keeping in touch with their Computer Aided Drug Design (CADD) department in the research division.

At present this work is collaborative; we consider this a necessary prerequisite step at present to demonstrate to an industry partner, such as UCB or Janssen, that the Centre could provide consulting services for a fee in the future.

2.2 Molecular Modelling (UC4)

This use case brings together two of the Centre's flagship applications, HADDOCK and GROMACS. The use case connects the docking software HADDOCK to the Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulation suite, GROMACS, to enhance the systematic modelling of biomolecular interactions, leveraging the performance of HPC/HTC infrastructures supported by BioExcel. In this pilot use case, HADDOCK is used to generate models of biomolecular complexes and a sampling method, typically MD simulations performed using GROMACS, is used after docking to evaluate the stability of the best cluster representatives generated by HADDOCK.

HADDOCK generates atomic 3D models of biomolecular interactions using any experimental information available, gathers them into clusters based on 3D similarities and finally ranks them with a simple yet very efficient scoring function. However, it sometimes remains challenging to rank the models that resemble the experimentally determined native structure (native-like model) at the top and to discriminate true biomolecular interactions from artificially predicted interfaces. We intend to investigate if short molecular dynamics (MD) simulations could help distinguish near-native from wrong models using a set of complexes generated with HADDOCK. The workflow is described in detail in D2.4⁹ and aims to:

- Sort native-like models from non-native-like models
- Improve HADDOCK's scoring, based either on empirical parameters or on energy terms derived from the sampling method
- Get insights into the likeliness of a given biomolecular interaction

The first results ran on a dataset of 11 protein-protein complexes and 7 protein-peptide complexes show promising results to improve the discrimination of native-like from non-native like interfaces when the HADDOCK score is not discriminant. MD simulations of 50ns, in duplicates, were performed using GROMACS 2016 and the CHARMM36m force field. The interface root mean square deviations (i-RMSD) to the starting structures over time and the persistence of residual contacts at the interface reveal insights into the stability and specificity of the interfaces. However, non-bonded energy terms derived from the MD were not meaningful in the context of short simulations. These findings demonstrate the promising added value of systematic short MD simulations when the

⁹ *Final Release of Workflows and Modular Tools for User Services*, BioExcel Deliverable 2.4. In review. Available from www.bioexcel.eu from November, 2018.

HADDOCK score is not discriminant, as a post-docking refinement that would focus on the stability of modelled interfaces.

Under the scope of BioExcel-1, we have also initiated three different workflows with collaborators: one that relies on remote and loose communication between services, another one that relies on cloud computing and Docker applications and finally a last one, geared toward industry, that investigates the performance of a difference sampling method.

1. Through a collaborative partnership with the **group Dr. Daan Geerke (molecular toxicology group, VU Amsterdam)**, we integrated HADDOCK in MDstudio, a microservice-based molecular dynamics workflows developed in his group with the support of the Dutch e-Science center¹⁰.
2. We have been contacted by **Wolfgang Gentsch, from Ubercloud¹¹**, who wanted to test a Docker container optimized for MD simulations on Microsoft Azure. We wrote a proposal that has been approved by Microsoft and got granted 5000 core hours for a preliminary test. Proven its efficiency, this workflow could be offered as a service, typically for industrial partners who have interest into the development of pharmacological leads, and cloud computing setup is the only sustainable solution to meet on-demand the users' needs.
3. Through a recent collaboration with **Dr. Silvia Lovera (UCB, Belgium)**, we are testing a new sampling protocol, namely Adaptive Sampling, and comparing how it performs in recovering native-like solution compared to classical MD. This collaboration, which was the result of the BioExcel visit to UCB, enables implementation of a workflow to identify true binders from non-binders for a set off small ligand interactions with target proteins, provided by our collaborators at UCB.

All the work behind this pilot use case is collaborative, which required different skills (IT, simulations, web design, etc.) for execution. With this approach, we hope in BioExcel-2 to continue benchmarking and shaping the protocol to meet the interests of our partners, but also to put in production the existing workflow using MDstudio.

2.3 Virtual Screening (UC5)

The Virtual Screening pilot use case brought project partners together with Nostrum Biodiscovery. It has been successful in a different number of ways:

1. Development of the software needed for the pipeline, which involves docking procedures, small molecules database retrieval and pocket detection obliged us to extend the BioExcel building blocks offering, making it wider and compelling. Early testing on a well characterised enzyme, the Pyruvate Kinase (see D2.4⁹) helped us to discover issues and improve both the software library and the pipeline.

¹⁰ See <https://www.research-software.nl/software/mdstudio>

¹¹ <https://www.theubercloud.com/>

2. As a productive computational technique of interest to the pharmaceutical field, which has drawn the attention of Nostrum Biodiscovery. These are a BSC spinoff company mainly focused on helping larger pharmaceutical customers to maximize the success of their drug discovery pipeline for generating new candidate medicines for development in clinical trials.
3. As a scientific study, in collaboration with Nostrum Biodiscovery, being run successfully on the BSC supercomputing infrastructures. The project is centered on the well characterised Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) which are transmembrane receptors located on the cell membrane. They are implicated in the oncogenic transformation of various types of cells, therefore representing an important drug target. The pipeline being used runs a virtual screening including ensemble docking with a large number of small molecules, with target ensembles extracted from a set of 1 microsecond-length molecular dynamics simulations of 7 different EGFR modeled mutations. An extended description can be found in D2.4⁹.

Notably, this use case gave us the opportunity to test our software library with a real scientific project, with the direct help of a pharmaceutical company. An important lesson learned from the process is the time needed to perform a complex scientific use case, usually not feasible during the lifetime of a project like this. Thanks to this fruitful collaboration, Nostrum Biodiscovery will join BioExcel-2, which will allow the continuation of this project, its extension, and the starting of new and even more ambitious projects.

2.4 Multi-scale modeling of molecular basis for odor and taste (UC3)

Development of a new and modern QM/MM interface for the quantum mechanical CPMD program¹² to overcome the main issues of the original interface: bad parallel performance, limited force-field availability, and non-free code. These issues probably contributed to hamper a wider spread of QM/MM approaches in the CPMD community¹³. The new interface managed to solve all these problems by coupling CPMD with the flexible GROMACS code. In this context, UC3 allowed us to apply and test the new interface on a real size, biologically-interesting problem, validating it and assessing its accuracy.

The biological system investigated in this use case is the enzyme adenylyl cyclase (AC) binding to the G-protein “Gas” and an ATP substrate. The work undertaken in this UC is part of a wider project in collaboration with the *Human Brain Project*¹⁴ (HBP) that focuses on understanding the mechanism how this binding stimulates the synthesis of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) from ATP substrate, amplifying signal transduction in the brain. A multi-scale approach, here a QM/MM one, is essential because the synthesis of cAMP through the so-called ATP cyclization involves a chemical reaction, but the system is much too large to be

¹² <http://cpmd.org>

¹³ For example, both the limited force-fields and the runtimes of the existing interface were both cited as issues during the 2017 Community Forum.

¹⁴ <https://www.humanbrainproject.eu/>

fully treated at quantum level. The systems AC bound to Gas (AC:Gas) and AC:Gas in complex with an ATP strand in the reactive conformation (AC:Gas:ATP) have been investigated by using both the popular original QM/MM interface, and the new and more efficient QM/MM interface. The comparison focuses mainly on the reproducibility of relevant structural features of the system (H-bonding network, ion coordination and stability, etc.) with the new interface, and on the estimation of the free energy barrier of the chemical reaction. A detailed analysis of the comparison will be published at the end of the project in collaboration with HBP, while the models built with the original and the new QM/MM interface (including the ones simulated with the original interface that resulted unstable, and which brought us to develop a multi-step iterative procedure described in Deliverables 2.3 and 2.4 in order to find a stable model minimizing the computational resources) will be available on the BioExcel website.

The HBP research group involved in this study is one of the five groups dedicated to molecular simulation in the Brain Simulation Platform (i.e. sub-project 6 or SP6) of HBP. The task of this research team is to provide atomistic information of enzyme-catalyzed chemical reactions and of protein-ligand binding and unbinding processes that govern neuronal cascades. As molecular modelers, their interest in AC is to understand how the binding of Gas stimulates cAMP synthesis. The collaboration with BioExcel was rather natural because the BioExcel unit that led UC3 has the expertise in hybrid QM/MM approaches required to study such large systems, and at the same time it was interested in applying the QM/MM interface in development to a real biological relevant system.

Initially, in order to identify the system to investigate and develop a strategy, the interaction with HBP research group was rather intense. In fact, the study was hampered by the fact that only the X-ray structures of AC bound to Gas were available. Really, a structure with an ATP mimic was also available, though the ATP is not in a reactive conformation. HBP finally proposed to use the last one as starting structure and the BioExcel team performed preliminary classical molecular dynamics in order to bring the system towards a reactive conformation before changing the level of theory to QM/MM in order to describe the chemical reaction at DFT level. At this point the interaction with HBP kept regular in order to report and discuss the status of the project, but not frequent as before because the timescales of performing QM/MM simulations and collecting enough statistics are usually rather long: at least 6 months, unless meanwhile stability problems arise in the simulations, as it happened initially in our case, and which brought us to develop the multi-step iterative workflow described in Deliverables 2.3 and 2.4.

The collaborative project with HBP is mainly a research project. The kind of interactions with the partner and the timescales described above are common for such kind of projects. However, these large and computational demanding projects can extend beyond the typical timeframe of a PhD or a postdoc contract, and this can make it difficult to keep the project alive. In our case this is possible thanks to the additional financial support of the partner that is funded over a period of time longer than the traditional scientific project.

This UC operated much like a traditional research collaboration. The relationship was symmetric; each partner brought expertise to the problem and each partner funded their own contribution. The collaboration satisfied the research agendas of both parties, but in this case, it was not the case that one party brought a problem and the other party brought a solution. A project such as the HBP would not normally subcontract research or software development work, so the most likely mode for future collaboration with this type of partner would be through the development and submission of a research proposal, and the award of public funding. It should be noted, however, that HBP does sometimes issue calls for proposals to work in particular areas and responding to calls such as this provides a mechanism to offer our expertise to such a project in the future.

2.5 High Throughput Workflow for Cancer Genome Sequencing Data (UC1)

The motivation for this use case was to find an existing workflow in the field of genomics which to date had not run with large-scale HPC, but which had the potential to be substantially more useful if it could be run more quickly. This was interesting as a pilot because genomics is a growing area in which BioExcel has an interest, despite it not being the primary focus of the centre's work. It also provides a link to "traditional" bioinformatics, an area in which -- with a few notable exceptions -- large-scale HPC is less widely used than, for instance, in molecular simulation. Much of the large-scale work in this area has been based on High Throughput Computing, and is based on models which would not necessarily scale to exascale. One aim of this use case was to explore whether a workflow from this field could be adapted to make good use of more traditional HPC resources. The use case also allowed us to explore how to best package up and distribute the workflow and its components to a wider audience. A collaboration was established with researchers from the Institute of Genetic and Molecular Medicine (IGMM) at the University of Edinburgh¹⁵.

Working with the researchers in IGMM, we developed Python-based workflows to perform genome sequence quality control and alignment. An original workflow description can be found in Deliverable 2.2 (Fig 4.7) and Deliverable 2.3¹⁶ (Figs. 2 and 3). As work progressed, we concentrated our efforts on improving the scalability, flexibility, speed and usability of the first two stages, which were the most well understood but time-consuming stages to execute for our partners. Working with partners, we were able to understand the workflow as currently executed, including the tools and data required for each stage. Prior to this work, the workflow had never previously been automated from start to finish, and required manual intervention at several stages. Previously, it was left to the user to ensure that each tool used in their workflow was installed correctly, and to make sure that all required files were available. The user also had to manually check the output from the FastQC tool¹⁷ to ensure that the sequence files were of suitable quality, and manually perform trimming stages if needed. The user would then pass the correct files to each individual stage in *alignment*. This can be made

¹⁵ <https://www.ed.ac.uk/igmm>

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1060946>

¹⁷ <https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>

easier to an extent by developing simple shell scripts, as was the case with our partners, but altering the workflow or running with different options can become tedious. For our partners, “time-to-result” was the most important factor when executing such workflows, so automation alone provides a useful improvement.

In developing the workflow, we considered several options, focusing on BCBio¹⁸, CWL¹⁹ and Python. As discussed in Deliverable 2.3, we found issues with both BCBio and CWL for our specific use case needs. In future, these may become options, such as using CWL to automate parts of our workflow, but this is beyond the scope of our work to date. We also performed benchmarking of the most time-consuming stages, to see where bottlenecks may be occurring. We found that scaling for parts of the Alignment stage (in particular the stages using GATK²⁰ version 3 and BWA²¹) showed inefficient use of a higher number of cores. We also found that a recently released update to GATK, starting with version 4.0 which switched to using Spark/Hadoop for performing multithreaded execution, not only scaled well across a whole node, but also allows execution of GATK tools across multiple nodes. More details can be found in Deliverable 2.4⁹.

The work undertaken in this UC is of the type that a CoE could do on behalf of researchers. Some aspects of this UC worked well, others less so, and we will now briefly describe some lessons learned from this UC which could help guide how it should undertake projects of this type in the future.

Many researchers are focused primarily on the delivery of their next piece of research. For this reason, it is very common to make the best use of the tools that are currently available to achieve the ends of the experiments being done. The researchers’ use of the tools is often imaginative and innovative, but in many cases, researchers do not have the time, incentive or skills to step back to look at how the tools could be improved. This is certainly an area where a CoE could add value to the science and progress in the field in general, even if the researchers do not necessarily perceive that the CoE is adding value to their work. This is understandable; in fact, it is often the case that the reward from work undertaken to improve tools is not received for some time after the work was done, and input provided by a particular researcher is likely to benefit *other* researchers in future.

This issue was apparent in the collaboration undertaken with IGMM at several stages. The researchers at IGMM were helpful throughout the work in the UC, but their priorities were such that they were not able to engage in a deep collaboration. This in itself is not problematic, but it explains various aspects of how work on this UC unfolded: it sometimes felt like they were helping *us* rather than the CoE helping them. There are lessons that the CoE can learn from this in terms of thinking about how to best collaborate with such groups. It was also apparent in the starting point from which we worked; example scripts provided by the partner for stages of the workflow had been put together by different

¹⁸ <https://bcbio-nextgen.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹⁹ <https://www.commonwl.org>

²⁰ <https://software.broadinstitute.org/gatk/>

²¹ <http://bio-bwa.sourceforge.net>

researchers over periods of time. The researchers had a good knowledge of what they did, and they had been used and tested widely enough that they knew that they worked. They also knew how long it took them to run on cases they had tried. There was, however, a gap in the understanding of how the scripts would perform in different contexts (e.g. on different computer systems) or why the performance was as it was. This is another example of a skillset that a CoE could bring to help accelerate a group's research.

The UC brought experience in working in a fast-moving field where plans had to be changed to address developments in the application area and in software developed by third parties (such as the new Spark-based version of GATK), and also offered insight into working in an area which is more removed from the project's core codes. In both cases lessons learned will be incorporated into future work in the Centre.

2.6 Summary & Comparison

Table 2 below summarises the use cases described above, and highlights important attributes to compare aspects of the various use cases.

Table 2: Comparison of Use Cases

	Free Energy Simulations of Biomolecular Complexes (UC2)	Biomolecular Recognition (UC4)	Virtual Screening (UC5)	Multi-scale modeling of molecular basis for odor and taste (UC3)	High Throughput Workflow for Cancer Genome Sequencing Data (UC1)
Main Goal(s)	Application of new tools for automated generation of protein and DNA mutations and calculation of the free energies of the resulting complexes and provision of web-based interface	Automating the modelling of biomolecular interactions by leveraging the performance of HPC/HTC infrastructure using docking and molecular simulation techniques	Automating the prediction of potent and specific inhibitor leads	Automating the modelling of biomolecular interactions by leveraging the performance of HPC/HTC infrastructure using docking and molecular simulation techniques	Implement new workflow and package for distribution. If time allows, optimise.
Problems addressed	Tools remove manual steps needed to generate mutants, model the complexes and compute the FE	Answers research questions about a problem that requires a quantum mechanical treatment such as a chemical reaction involved in signaling cascade.	Avoid the laborious process of manually executing numerous steps of docking, scoring, selection etc. of potential drug candidates	High-throughput experimental techniques generate a wealth of qualitative and quantitative data, but the structural dimension is often missing. This calls for complementary modelling approaches.	This workflow currently involves manual steps, and has never been fully automated. Sections have typically been run on desktops or small clusters and could benefit from scaling to reduce time to solution.

Collaborators	Boehringer Ingelheim, Janssen	Utrecht University & KTH (including those outside BioExcel)	Nostrum Biodiscovery	Human Brain Project	IGMM (Researchers working on full-genome analysis)
Expertise contributed by CoE	Expert knowledge in Free Energy calculations; Advanced tools for modelling and simulations	Leading expertise in molecular recognition and molecular dynamics simulations	Supercomputer implementation and workflow development	Code development. Specific application expertise (CPMD). Some expertise on methods (multiscale modelling).	General computation & workflow expertise. (Not code or application-area specific).
Other resources offered by CoE in addition to personnel	MPG Compute Resources	Local computational resources (cluster in Utrecht) to benchmark use cases with GROMACS.	Local computational resources (supercomputers in BSC: Marenostrum IV, Minotauro) to test and run VS workflow	Large amount of computational resources for QM/MM simulations awarded by some European supercomputing centers through open calls	Access to various HPC systems including ARCHER (Tier 1) and Cirrus (Tier 2)
Length of Project	3 years	3 years	3 years	3 years	3 years
Effort over project period	~8 PM	~2PM (BioExcel) + ~10PM (collaborators)	~5PM	~3PM (BioExcel) + ~3PM (BioExcel partners, charged elsewhere) + ~12PM (collaborator)	~8 PM
Granularity of Interaction	Long term collaboration. Meetings at least once per year, email as required	Meetings every other month and regular email exchange on a monthly basis	Meetings every month	Long term. Meetings a 2-3 times per month, email as required.	Long term. Meetings a 2-3 times per year, email as required.
Future Potential	Yes, this is part of a long-term research programme aiming to developing a complete open-source alchemical free energy pipeline, supporting protein and nucleic acid mutations as well as ligand modifications, supporting	Yes, this is a long-term research programme we are joining and will be further funded/developed. We have multiple concrete projects that could make use of the platform developed within the UC.	Yes, this is a long-term project that is being developed and tested together with Nostrum Biodiscovery. Nostrum is interested in using the technology for different projects, with possible extensions.	No immediate follow-on. This research project will finish with the validation of the QM/MM interface and answers to the scientific questions of interest to HBP. Similar systems could be investigated with very similar approach if requested	Unlikely to progress. Collaborator's priorities have changed.

	multiple molecular mechanics force fields.			(qualified personnel and considerable computational resources are required).	
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3 Mini Projects

As well as the pilot use cases described above, we have engaged in a number of mini projects that are driven by our understanding of user needs. They go beyond the work described in the original BioExcel-1 proposal. These were started towards the end of BioExcel-1; in some cases these are opportunities that have arisen from the work we have done in the project, in others these provide stepping stones to work proposed for BioExcel-2.

3.1 Standardization of BioExcel Building blocks for easier deployment in different computational environments

This mini project aims to adapt the demonstration workflows to different environments that still require some degree of manual tuning, complicating the distribution to final users.

The project links in with work underway in ELIXIR²². Engagement with initiatives such as this brings BioExcel to a wider audience and provides useful tools to the community that in future, BioExcel would be well-placed to offer support for on a consultancy basis.

The main tasks planned for this mini project are as follows:

1. Develop automatic adaptors of the **BioExcel Building Blocks (biobb)** library for a series of deployment options:
 - a. **CWL**²³ specification (automatic adaptation to CWL 1.1. just released). CWL complaint managers.
 - b. **Conda**²⁴ **packaging**, and integration into **BioConda**²⁵ registry, which provides system-agnostic executable environments.
 - c. **Galaxy ToolShed**²⁶, to spread the user scope and bridge with more genomics oriented workflows usually available in this context.

²² <https://www.elixir-europe.org>

²³ <https://www.commonwl.org/>

²⁴ <https://conda.io/docs/>

²⁵ <https://bioconda.github.io/>

²⁶ <https://galaxyproject.org/toolshed/>

- d. **GA4GH TES** ²⁷ , and **WES** ²⁸ No real software follows such specification yet, however there is a general agreement in the need of considering it.
 - e. Additionally, we will build recipes for including **PyCOMPSs**²⁹ in the same deployment environments, especially **BioConda**.
2. Build software containers to deploy components of the library, and implement automatic orchestration of the containers using PyCOMPSs, CWL, but also new popular tools like Kubernetes³⁰. This approach links directly with the guidelines of the Tools Platform from ELIXIR³¹. Containers will be included in ELIXIR.

Work started fairly recently, but has already produced the first outcomes. Software packaging initiatives such as Python PyPI (pip), (bio)conda, and biocontainers have been studied and tested. The first implementations of the BioExcel building blocks, divided according to their functionality (“common”, “io”, “md”) are already available:

biobb_common: Python pip³², bioconda³³, biocontainers³⁴.

biobb_io: Python pip³⁵, bioconda³⁶, biocontainers³⁷.

biobb_md: Python pip³⁸, bioconda³⁹, biocontainers⁴⁰.

Work to date has involved only BioExcel partners, but possible collaborators identified are CWL, Galaxy and GA4GH. The work of the type being done in this mini project is unlikely to be done as consultancy work, but in bundling and providing standard building blocks it provides a basis for future consultancy work.

A page summarising the current status of the work is available⁴¹, and a short update will be provided in D3.5⁴², due at the end of the project.

²⁷ <https://github.com/ga4gh/task-execution-schemas>

²⁸ <https://github.com/ga4gh/workflow-execution-service-schemas>

²⁹ <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1094342015594678>

³⁰ <https://kubernetes.io/>

³¹ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/platforms/tools>

³² <https://pypi.org/project/biobb-common/>

³³ https://anaconda.org/bioconda/biobb_common

³⁴ https://quay.io/repository/biocontainers/biobb_common

³⁵ <https://pypi.org/project/biobb-io/>

³⁶ https://anaconda.org/bioconda/biobb_io

³⁷ https://quay.io/repository/biocontainers/biobb_io

³⁸ <https://pypi.org/project/biobb-md/>

³⁹ https://anaconda.org/bioconda/biobb_md

⁴⁰ https://quay.io/repository/biocontainers/biobb_md

⁴¹ https://bioexcel.eu/research/projects/biobb_standardization/

⁴² BioExcel Deliverable D3.5, in preparation (Available from January, 2019 at www.bioexcel.eu)

3.2 Biobb Web Server

This mini project aims to build a Graphical User Interface (GUI) on top of the developed BioExcel building blocks. The aim is to have a GUI to further increase the usability of BioExcel workflows and tools for the significant group of potential users that are not familiar with HPC programming, but have a real interest in this topic, which includes those users from pharmaceutical companies who prefer to work with graphical interfaces, and also entry level users.

Work on this project has started, and a first prototype of the interface is being developed at the time of writing. This prototype will include basic functionalities, such as input/upload of structures, and visualization. Next steps are implementing an interactive structure checking stage, and connection between the web server and on-demand, deployable Virtual Machines, running the actual workflows. Analysis and a possible connection to HPC supercomputers will be studied in the last stages of the project.

Again, the type of work being done in this mini project is probably not the kind of work which would be offered as consultancy, but it could act as a demonstrator to potential users as to what can be done with the BioExcel building blocks. It is possible that in future, work could be commissioned to provide access to new building blocks through this graphical interface.

3.3 Workflow building blocks as KNIME nodes

This mini project⁴³ is strongly related to the previous one both in its final goal (reaching the pharmaceutical field), and in its approach (GUI). Here, instead of creating a new GUI, we want to try to use a popular workflow platform in the cheminformatics world for data analysis, statistics and visualization: KNIME. KNIME is an easy and intuitive drag and drop based GUI, with more than 1,500 free nodes (equivalent to our BioExcel building blocks). New nodes can be implemented and contributed by the community, many are free (e.g. Vernalis⁴⁴) and some require commercial licences (e.g. Schrödinger⁴⁵).

At the time of writing, the project has successfully passed the phase 1, which was the analysis of feasibility. As KNIME is a java-based application, a new wrapper around each of the BioExcel building blocks needs to be implemented, using the KNIME java Standard Development Kit (SDK)⁴⁶. We have been able to install and configure the required environment to build a new KNIME node, and we have successfully port the first building block (retrieval of a PDB structure from the MMB mirror⁴⁷). Now we are starting the phase 2, which consists of porting the rest of the biobb building blocks, divided into different categories, according to their functionalities.

⁴³ https://bioexcel.eu/research/projects/biobb_knime/

⁴⁴ <https://www.knime.com/book/vernal-is-nodes-for-knime-trusted-extension>

⁴⁵ <https://www.schrodinger.com/KNIME-Extensions>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/knime/knime-sdk-setup>

⁴⁷ https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb_io/blob/master/biobb_io/mmb_api/pdb.py

Collaborations in this project have not yet started, but possible collaborators identified are KNIME developers, as we have already spotted some shared interests with other communities that we would like to discuss directly with them.

This work helps to broaden the community of potential users of the BioExcel building blocks and use of these nodes is another area in which BioExcel could offer consultancy in future.

3.4 BioExcel workflow repository as a one-stop-shop to find and explore the workflows, independent of workflow engine

BioExcel have developed several workflows and workflow building blocks (D2.4⁹). These are exemplified for multiple workflow systems, including CWL, PyCOMPSs and Jupyter Notebooks, as well as being available as containers and virtual machine images. These workflow definitions are currently made available as a series of GitHub repositories⁴⁸, but do not currently have a user-level presentation for more accessible browsing before the user decides to try executing the workflow.

Workflow repositories such as myExperiment⁴⁹ can in theory be utilized for publishing the BioExcel workflows, since it includes a graphical view of the workflow and rich annotations of their use. However the design of the BioExcel workflows have highlighted a new modality in multiple languages and containers representing the same conceptual workflow. In addition the aging myExperiment code base, managed by BioExcel partner The University of Manchester, does not have any particular support for CWL or PyCOMPSs.

The University of Manchester has developed the SEEK4Science platform⁵⁰, which provides a structured digital asset repository for projects and collaborations. In this mini-project we are extending the SEEK platform to add an initial support for Workflows, but unlike myExperiment it will work more like a catalogue (e.g. with links to GitHub and Docker Hub) rather than a repository where workflow definition files are deposited.

This will then form the basis for a BioExcel-customized SEEK installation for presenting the workflow building blocks and examples, allowing for multiple platform representation of the same workflow, which can be organized with related SEEK entries for the BioExcel pilot use cases and their results.

The initial development started by BioExcel to add workflow support to SEEK will be further extended from 2019 onwards in emerging EU projects where UNIMAN is a partner; [IBISBA](https://www.ibisba.eu/)⁵¹ is developing functionality for execution of CWL workflows⁵² to its SEEK-based IBISBAHub, while *EOSC-Life*⁵³ will use SEEK as a

⁴⁸ <https://github.com/bioexcel>

⁴⁹ <https://www.myexperiment.org/>

⁵⁰ <http://www.seek4science.org/>

⁵¹ IBISBA (H2020 730976), <https://www.ibisba.eu/>

⁵² <https://www.esciencelab.org.uk/projects/ibisba/#escience-lab-contributions>

⁵³ EOSC-Life (H2020 824087)

starting point to develop a mechanism for federated publishing and and sharing workflows across the European Open Science Cloud⁵⁴ for execution on shared computational resources. While we recognise the benefits these later co-developments can later bring for the BioExcel workflow repository, we also see this mini-project as a stepping stone for publication of BioExcel workflows into the larger community of European scientific workflow cloud infrastructure.

3.5 Integration and documentation of a new user interface to access atom properties dynamically and efficiently during GROMACS simulations

This mini project is delivering specific changes to GROMACS to address feature requests from collaborators at MPG. It involves changing GROMACS to add infrastructure to support new kinds of simulations, guided by restraints derived from other data such as Cryo-EM, and/or retrospectively observing how well simulations conform with such data (when not guided).

Though Cryo-EM data is being used here to evaluate the technique, the infrastructure for efficiently retrieving atom information during simulation runtime will be applicable to any type of external input about a system, from small-angle x-ray scattering (SAXS) and small-angle neutron scattering (SANS) to secondary structure information, etc. The code is already being used (in alpha-testing) by a researcher from Polytechnical University of Gdansk.

This kind of development is exactly the kind of thing that a client might want to commission. They're unlikely to have the combination of C++, GROMACS, and scientific expertise in house, don't have a long term need for it, could derive strong commercial value for it, so should want to contract for the work.

Additional GROMACS community meetings were also organised in the context of this mini project.

This work is still underway at the time of writing; a short update will be provided in D3.5.

3.6 Protocol for meta-dynamics with GROMACS and HADDOCK for docking

This mini project was to contribute to the development of a new protocol for meta-dynamics with GROMACS and HADDOCK. BioExcel effort was used to build on work already underway, but which required additional work to bring it to publication. The work is now ready for publication and has been submitted as a preprint⁵⁵.

The mini project is now complete, but it is likely that related work will continue in BioExcel-2, which includes the study of antibodies as a subject of particular interest. The technique developed and applied in the work supported by this mini project is relevant to the studies of antibodies proposed for BioExcel-2.

⁵⁴ <https://www.slideshare.net/JISC/the-european-open-science-cloud-just-what-is-it>

⁵⁵ A. Basciu, *An enhanced-sampling MD-based protocol for molecular docking*; <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2018/10/03/434092>

This project built on a collaboration with a PhD student who visited BioExcel partner UU and demonstrates the impact that student visits to BioExcel groups can have. BioExcel-2 includes plans to welcome visitors (such as those such funded through HPC-Europa) to BioExcel partner sites.

The collaborative project brought together experts in meta-dynamics with application (HADDOCK) experts. The work undertaken in this mini project was representative of work which the CoE could do in future. The contribution here built on work already underway; the CoE was able to contribute expertise and effort in order to increase the quality of the research and to bring the work to publication. Again, with this UC, it was the Centre that identified the opportunity for collaboration, but building relationships such as these is key to establishing the value of BioExcel in the wider research community. The protocol might also be interesting for the CoE in future since it uses GROMACS for meta-dynamics.

This work is feeding into a proposal for an ITN on the subject of antibodies, which is currently in preparation, and it also helped to cement the relationship with the group from Cagliari with which BioExcel worked to deliver the successful Summer School in 2018. There are plans to continue these summer schools in BioExcel-2.

4 Workflows as a Sustainability Activity

The first three mini projects described above were proposed after discussions in WP5 about sustainability activities. The need to support users in the pharmaceutical industry triggered the possibility to work on a well-designed graphical user interface (GUI) and on KNIME nodes. Related to that, a focus group meeting has been organized by BioExcel partner, Ian Harrow Consulting, with the purpose of gathering a group of experts to test design ideas for products and services that aim to improve productivity in the application of biomolecular tools for research and development in pharma and agri-food industry. The first prototypes mentioned for the GUI and KNIME nodes will be presented to representatives of pharmaceutical companies, to obtain feedback on their needs and the early prototypes.

The BioExcel building blocks constitute a concrete output from BioExcel-1 of immediate interest to the research community. The availability of these building blocks allows BioExcel to promote their use, and offer our help in using them. The work in the mini projects described above was planned with industry users in mind, and we hope that support for the building blocks is something that could be offered in the context of consultancy in the future. This will be explored in more detail during the focus group meeting mentioned above.

Further discussion of how the workflow work could contribute to the CoE's sustainability will be included in D5.4, after the results from the focus group meeting have been taken into account.

In recent months, we have started to promote the BioExcel building blocks. They have been promoted at various conferences, focused on different fields: supercomputing, e.g.:

- Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing – PASC18⁵⁶
- Spanish Supercomputation Network user’s meeting – RES⁵⁷
- Software best practices in bioinformatics (Network Tools and Applications in Biology - Nettare⁵⁸)

We have also offered some sponsorship to these meetings to further boost the profile of BioExcel to these audiences. They will also be promoted in a big workshop that is being planned for the end of the year together with MolSSI⁵⁹ and BioSimSpace⁶⁰ projects, with a possible follow-up hosted by the MolSSI in Rutgers (US), within the timeframe of BioExcel-2.

5 Preparations for Future Consultancy Services

The work described above illustrates the many ways in which BioExcel-1 has laid the foundations for future consultancy work. The process takes time, and much of the work in this project has been about announcing our existence, building trust, and establishing a good reputation for the BioExcel brand. It can be seen that some of the most valuable relationships that have been established (for example with industry partners) have taken some time to develop, and have been the result of various related activities in the Centre.

After the initial exercise to understand the community landscape we began working on the pilot use cases and established a number of Interest Groups (IGs) whose membership increased steadily through the project. With the Industry IG in particular, we have taken care not to rush the process of building relationships with IG members and the communities to which they belong. Industry engagement with academic projects takes time and so costs money; a project such as BioExcel may only have one chance to establish a working relationship, so it has been important to have something concrete to show when approaching industry. Industry IG calls and the Community Forum provided us with the channels to talk to industry members, but it is the work that has been going on in the pilot use cases, along with related work underway in the partners’ research groups which has allowed the centre to get the attention of industry partners.

The Industry IG calls and BioExcel’s webinar series provided a way for participants to learn something about our work without having to invest time in travelling to events. Once they learned about our work, they were willing to invest some time in attending events such as the Community Forum, and the BioExcel-

⁵⁶ <https://pasc18.pasc-conference.org/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.res.es/en/events/12th-res-users-meeting-7th-hpc-advisory-council-conference>

⁵⁸ <http://www.igst.it/nettab/2018/>

⁵⁹ <https://molssi.org/>

⁶⁰ <https://biosimspace.org/>

SIG at ECCB, where we invited them to speak, thereby learning more about their current priorities and pain points. These events (and, importantly, additional direct communication with project partners) led ultimately to mini projects of particular interest to the industry collaborators and joint research proposals, such as the *Consortium for Integrated Modelling of Antibodies (IMAbs)* described below. During 2018, we have also started site visits to further bolster our relationships and to learn more about the needs of the specific companies.

We are now approaching the point where the various prerequisites for offering consultancy to industrial partners are coming together: the companies trust us and understand our expertise, and we understand their interests and pain points.

5.1 Consortium for Integrated Modelling of Antibodies

The BioExcel-1 partner, Ian Harrow Consulting introduced other partners, Erik Lindahl (KTH), Alexandre Bonvin (U. Utrecht) and Vera Matser (EMBL-EBI) to Richard Norman, the project manager for the AbVance Project⁶¹ of the Pistoia Alliance which includes the pharma companies UCB, AstraZeneca and MedImmune. They worked together to build a consortium focused on Integrated Modelling of Antibodies (IMAbs) and applied for public funding for a four-year Innovative Training Network (ITN) under call H2020-MSCA-ITN-2018. Although the funding was unsuccessful, it has resulted in a promising collaboration and the intention to seek further public funding opportunities together, including a plan to resubmit an updated bid in January, 2019. This collaborative activity has also fed into the successful bid for BioExcel-2 which now includes Richard Norman as a consultant and use cases for integrated modelling of Antibody (Ab) structures and computational Ab drug design.

5.2 Site Visits

Site visits to pharmaceutical companies, organised by BioExcel-1 partner, Ian Harrow Consulting are a key activity that we have undertaken. These are a considerable investment by the project; they require much planning and typically involve a number of senior members of the project meeting with a relevant group of users of biomolecular software for modelling and drug design at a particular company. This cost is invaluable because it helps us to reach a deep understanding of their needs, it gives us an opportunity to present the latest developments and plans for BioExcel core tools and most importantly, leads to follow-up actions and plans to build meaningful collaborations. This deep understanding of user needs informs our software development roadmap and gives the potential for future professional support services.

Site visits began in early 2018 with a site visit to Janssen near Antwerp. This brought together key BioExcel partners expert in GROMACS, PMX and HADDOCK, with two key external modelling collaborators. Janssen's *Biomolecular Modelling and Computational Drug Design* group hosted the one day event which began with presentation of their capabilities and key challenges. Following presentations by BioExcel partners and the other two collaborators we were able to identify follow-

⁶¹ <https://www.pistoiaalliance.org/abvance/>

up actions for ongoing collaboration. The modelling experts from Janssen attended both the BioExcel Community Forum and Summer School.

We also visited UCB's site near Brussels during May which proved to be equally fruitful. This visit was partly stimulated by building the iMAbs consortium described above. This strong relationship with UCB, begun with their representative, Dr Zara Sands joining the Scientific Advisory Board of BioExcel-1 in 2017. BioExcel partners visited UCB to understand better their capabilities and needs for Biomolecular modelling and Computational Drug Design. This has fostered collaborations with the potential for publication and professional consultancy support in future.

Following the visit to UCB they sent some of their group to the Bonvin laboratory at the University of Utrecht on April 15th, for a training workshop on HADDOCK, at neutral cost. This was a customised workshop, for 5 attendees from UCB. An online tutorial⁶² was especially developed for this purpose, and access was provided to an upcoming version of the software (v2.4). UCB was charged €605 (including VAT) for the workshop, which included a 50% special rebate from BioExcel. The workshop was thus offered at on a cost-neutral basis. The intention was not to profit from this initial session, but a fee was charged to demonstrate that a commercial entity would be willing to pay for this type of training. The workshop was very well received by the UCB researchers who gave as feedback that this was the best tutorial they have followed so far, of much higher quality than any commercial offering. This suggests that there is a market for courses such as this, and that such activities could support the sustainability of the Centre in the future.

Since that time UCB have purchased a number of HADDOCK licenses for their sites in Belgium and the United Kingdom. Furthermore, the Bonvin group have been collaborating with Sebastian Kelm at UCB (Slough, UK site) to benchmark HADDOCK for antibody-antigen modelling, compared to other docking software. This collaboration work is expected to lead to a publication. This strong relationship serves as an excellent model for working with further pharmaceutical companies.

6 Future Plans

BioExcel-1 continues for a further two months, to the end of December 2018, to be immediately followed by BioExcel-2. The Centre will continue to be known as *BioExcel* and from a public point-of-view the transition to BioExcel-2 should have few, if any, noticeable consequences. For this reason, we will continue our community-facing work, such as webinars, support of the *AskBioExcel* forum and discussion with industry through into the follow-on project. We *do* expect to make changes around the Interest Groups in BioExcel-2. IGs will not continue in their present form, but we will instead offer people the opportunity to “join” a single BioExcel community, and to state their interests so that we can engage with appropriate subgroups of users. It is planned that this community will also include

⁶² <http://www.bonvinlab.org/education/HADDOCK-local-tutorial/>

people attending BioExcel training events, forum users and attendees of our meetings. Details of users will be stored in a single place, allowing us to keep track of their interactions with the centre, but to do this in a way that is compliant with data protection legislation. It is expected that industry calls will continue, but more emphasis will be placed on bilateral engagement as opposed to a single industry interest group.

6.1 BioExcel-2 Use Cases

Use cases will also play an important role in BioExcel-2, continuing to ensure that the work of the CoE is use-case driven.

The use case ***Biomolecular interactions engineering - application to antibody design*** builds on the establishment of the Consortium for Antibody Modelling and Computational Design described above. It addresses an area of particular interest in the pharmaceutical industry.

Key challenges in predicting and improving antibody binding to target proteins on the cell surface (so-called antigens), are 1) to reliably predict 3D structures of antibodies, in particular the Complementarity-Determining Regions (CDRs), 2) to model their binding mode and understand how the structure and motion of both molecules are altered in this process, and 3) to improve the binding affinity through systematic amino acid mutations. This use case aims at addressing all those points through an integrative approach combining key BioExcel components, namely GROMACS, HADDOCK and PMX. The necessary workflows will also be candidates for evaluating workflow technologies investigated elsewhere in the project.

Modeling of all pairwise human protein interactions - the interactome will look at bringing a structural dimension to studies of the interactions between proteins and other molecule and will also address the issue of predicting the form of the interactome given knowledge of the proteome. This study will require hundreds of thousands of docking runs, each requiring over 10 million CPU hours and generating ~1 Exabyte of data. The second challenge will require all-vs-all docking of proteins (approximately $20,000^2$ docking runs), then predicting binding affinity, possibly using molecular dynamics simulations. This would require in the order of 10 billion CPU hours and generate over 100 Exabytes of data. This use case also brings docking software such as HADDOCK together with MD (e.g. GROMACS).

IRB together with BSC have planned an ambitious use case in BioExcel-2, entitled ***Rational Drug Design***, which internally can be divided in 4 different configurable and interconnected workflows. The use case is built around the interests of pharmaceutical companies, who are heavy users of molecular simulation during the process of lead design and optimization, and constitute important actors for the long-term sustainability of the centre.

The use case takes full advantage of the technology designed and developed in BioExcel. Building blocks and workflows related to Molecular Dynamics simulations and Virtual Screening are the core of the proposed pipelines. Much

complex modules, though, will need to be implemented around them, such as biased MD methods or High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA). The collaboration with Nostrum Biodiscovery, established during use case work in BioExcel 1 which led to them joining as a partner in BioExcel-2, will continue to be essential for the progress of the whole use case, for its total orientation towards the pharmaceutical industry.

The final UC in BioExcel-2 is entitled ***Phenomena that depend on electronic interactions: Proton dynamics & Fluorescent Proteins***. This use case will focus on modeling complex cases that go beyond what is possible with classical methods and employ QM/MM calculations that combine the GROMACS & CP2K engines for two test applications. Our first application is focused on electrospray ionization/ion mobility mass spectrometry (ESI/IM-MS), which is a key tool in proteomics to measure stoichiometry, shape and subunit architecture of protein complexes. Our second QM/MM application is fluorescence microscopy with fluorescent proteins that plays an increasing role in revealing living systems function and understanding diseases. This UC brings in CP2K, which is a new core code in BioExcel-2.

7 Conclusion

Throughout BioExcel-1, WP3 has worked on a broad range of activities designed to address the needs of the diverse biomolecular research community, from support for and engagement with academic and the specific goals of selected industry collaborators. Considerable groundwork has been put in place to build a capability to offer professional consultancy, building trust with potential future customers. This groundwork included the project's pilot use cases which provided insight into possible consultancy models and topics as well as delivering services such as webinars, support forums, and events which simultaneously allowed us to deliver on our aims to spread best practice, allow communities to learn about the work of the centre, and for us to learn more about the needs of the communities. The use cases also had concrete outcomes of their own, such as validation of code developments and making available workflows and workflow components.

As well as the services delivered by the centre and the significant development activities that have happened in WP1 and WP2, the project has provided opportunities for the partners to engage in a number of new proposals (such as those detailed in D3.2), some of which have led into further use-case work in BioExcel-2 which includes topics of specific interest to pharmaceutical and agri-food companies in future.